

The Pragmatic Functions of Code-Switching in Teacher-Student Conflict: A Study of EFL Classroom Exchanges in Cameroon

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Abstract:

In the context of EFL teaching, teachers often make it a principle to avoid the first language of the learners as much as possible. However, it is generally remarked that, in situations of teacher-student conflicts, a good number of EFL teachers in Cameroon use French systematically to perform a myriad of acts: trans language turns into a powerful resource. This therefore means that code switching, which is the usual bone of contention between EFL teachers and students, becomes a weapon. The present article focuses on the use of code switching in EFL classes. It seeks to find out how EFL teachers and students code-switch in the context of conflicts; it

equally aims at discovering their pragmatic functions as well as their perlocutionary effects. The data collection method was classroom observation in 35 classes. A total of 73 hours of English were observed and recorded in 20 secondary schools located in 6 regions of Cameroon. Upon transcription of the recorded lessons, 70 teacher-student classroom exchanges were selected for the purpose of analysis in accordance with Austin & Searle's theory of speech acts and Leech's theory of politeness. The findings revealed that though code-switching is generally avoided during English classes but it is frequently used by EFL teachers and students in classroom conflict situations in Cameroon. It was equally found out that there exists a correlation between language use and teacher-student conflict in the EFL class in Cameroon.

Keywords: *disagreement, interaction, classroom discourse, pragmatics, EFL.*

Resume:

Dans le cadre de l'enseignement de l'anglais comme langue étrangère, les enseignants en principe évitent au maximum de recourir à la première langue de l'apprenant. Cependant, on remarque qu'en général, en situations de conflits élèves-professeurs, un bon nombre d'enseignants d'anglais recourent systématiquement au français pour poser une pléthore d'actes pédagogiquement incorrects : l'alternance codique devient ainsi une ressource puissante. En d'autres termes, l'alternance codique souvent considérée comme une véritable pomme de discorde entre les professeurs d'anglais et les élèves francophones au Cameroun, plutôt qu'une ressource didactique, se transforme en une arme. Le présent article traite de l'usage de l'alternance codique et de leurs fonctions pragmatiques en situation de conflit pendant les cours d'anglais langue étrangère; notre objectif dans ce travail est de repérer les types d'alternance codique fréquemment utilisés en situation de conflits élève-professeur en classe ; il vise aussi à présenter les fonctions de ce phénomène linguistique dans ce contexte de même que leur effet sur les acteurs de la classe. Les données ont été collectées pendant la phase d'observation directe des cours

d'anglais dans 35 classes de 20 établissements d'enseignement secondaire situés dans 6 régions du Cameroun. 73 heures de cours ont été observées et enregistrées puis transcrites manuellement. Après la transcription, 70 échanges jugés conflictuels ont été sélectionnés aux fins d'analyse. Le cadre théorique utilisé dans la théorie de la politesse de Leech (1983). Les résultats auxquels nous sommes parvenus montrent qu'en situation de conflit, les enseignants tout comme les élèves violent les règles de politesse et recourent fréquemment à trois types d'alternance codique, pourtant prohibés en général pendant les cours d'anglais. L'analyse des mots a révélé qu'il existe une corrélation entre le type de discours tenu par les élèves et les professeurs et la survenue des conflits dans la classe.

Mots Clés: *Alternance codique, fonctions, pragmatique, conflits, échanges.*

Introduction

Code-switching has often been a bone of contention in the EFL class. Despite the institution of the bilingual game by the Ministry of secondary education in 2014, in general, English teachers strongly believe in the only English approach to ELT in Cameroon. Many English teachers easily take offence when students speak French during their classes. In the same vein, a good number of teachers avoid French as much as possible during their lessons, which remain the rarest opportunity of exposure for Francophone Cameroonian learners. The present paper set out to foreground the pragmatic roles of code-switching in situations of conflict in EFL classes. The problem raised in this article is that EFL teachers who generally forbid French during EFL classes, tend to use it abundantly in situations of conflicts. In addition, previous studies on code-switching in Cameroon have discussed its pedagogic merits in a bilingual context. Tabe(2023) studied the code-mixing and code-switching in Cameroon social media and found out that social media users switch and mix codes in the following way: from English to French, from English to Cameroon Pidgin English and from English to home languages .Ezemba et al (2022) analysed code-switching and code-mixing amongst the students of a catholic college in Buea-Muea and the findings of their research revealed that stylistic , social and grammatical factors motivated the use of code-switching during classroom interaction. Sokeng(2018) investigated the views of teachers and students about the practice of code-switching in the University of Yaounde I .

Djuidje (2007) examined code-switching and code-mixing in the speech of primary school students in Bamenda. The present research has a different orientation for it examines the uses of code switching in situations of conflict with a focus on its pragmatic functions. We will therefore try to provide answers to the following questions:

- What types of code-switching EFL teachers and students resort to in situations of conflict?
- What pragmatic purpose does code - switching serve in the EFL class in situations of conflict?

As far as method of research is concerned, direct classroom observation was used. In fact, 73 hours of English lessons were observed and recorded using a dictaphone in 35 classes of 20 schools in Cameroonian secondary private and government schools. Then these lessons were transcribed, and 70 teacher-students exchanges reminiscent of conflict were identified and analysed. The sampling method applied for data collection was purposive sampling: only exchanges that were reminiscent of conflict were selected. The theoretical framework used for the data analysis comprised Austin & Searle (1969) theory of speech acts and Leech (1983) theory of politeness and data is presented in tables, figures, and exchanges. The research was qualitative (70 exchanges were selected) and quantitative (the occurrence of an information in the corpus was counted; the frequency was calculated using descriptive statistics).

1. Presentation and discussion of the results

The analysis of the EFL teacher-student exchanges recorded during classroom observation and transcribed shows that a good number of the data showed that two forms of code switching were predominantly used by teachers in situations of disharmony: tag-switching and inter-sentential switching. EFL teachers often switched to French to carry out various acts in conflictual contexts. Similarly, we found out that EFL students generally switched to French, Camfranglais or Pidgin to perform many acts that either worsened disharmony or restored harmony. Unlike teachers, students often used tag-switching to express disagreement with the teacher when there was no harmony. Interestingly, we realized that EFL learners code-switched more than teachers did in situations of conflict. The abundant use of French by students portrays conflict in English Language classes because in a normal EFL class, the use of French is supposed to be rare. We then found out that the use of French was the main bone of contention between teachers and students since teachers often regard French as mere provocation during EFL classes, a blatant violation of all the politeness principles. In the corpus, instances of tag-switching and intersentential switching were found; we noticed that code switching was a usual communicative strategy in situations of disharmony.

1.1 The Types of Code-Switching

1.1.1 Use of tag-switching

In *The Oxford Companion English Language Dictionary* (1998), code-switching is defined as the movement from one language to another. According to Gumperz (1982: 59), it is the juxtaposition within the same speech exchange of passages belonging to two different grammatical systems or sub-systems. As far as tag-switching is concerned, it refers to the incorporation of a tag, an exclamation, or a parenthetical element in a language other than the rest of the sentence. This category of code-switching was abundantly used by teachers and students in situations of conflict. In Exchange 54

below, many instances of tag-switching were identified.

Exchange 54: Lycée de New, 3^e, February 2016, Douala

Situation: Three students came late and asked for permission to enter the class. The teacher asked one to enter and drove the two others away.

Ss: Toc toc toc

Teacher: Yes! What do you want? (Angrily)

The female st: Mme, we want to enter.

Teacher: You are late.

Ava: Please noon Mme.

Teacher: Ava, the girl, come in dear. You, va en balade!

Class: (screaming) Hooo Mme.

TeacherTeacher : Shut up, il y'a des élèves sur qui on peut compter et d'autres sur qui on ne peut pas.

A male st: Jamais, I am also student.

Teacher: Hey méfiez vous! Go far. I don't want to see you.

Bodo: la discrimination is not good.

Teacher: OK! Continue to behave like a mad man and I will let you in. n'importe quoi.

Bodo:Bodo : Me teacher ? N'importe quoi aussi

Class: (Laughters and noise and the teacher ignore Bodo).

Bodo: (Knocks after some minutes) toc toc. I cannot go hein Mme. Je m'enganban

Teacher: tsuip, cloose that door.

Bodo: I am a student, I also pay. Je wanda. Hum la Nga ci hein.

Teacher: Ca suffit. Class prefect, go and call the Discipline Master for me. I am the only person who decides in this class. Not you OK? When you are big, don't come to school.

Boy:Boy : (Leaving) Dieu est là.

Teacher: (Bursts into laughter) So you know God? Vraiment!

In the exchange above, the conflict was provoked by the teacher's unfair attitude; she did

not treat the three latecomers with justice. The language used by the teacher and the learners indicates disharmony. Several examples of tag-switching are presented in the table below.

Table 1. Examples of Tag-Switching Found in EX 54

N°	Teacher's utterances			N°	Learner's utterances		
	Locution	Illocution	Perlocution		Locution	Illocution	Perlocution
1	Ava, the girl come in dear. You, va en balade!	Welcoming the girl Driving the boy away	Complaints Screams	1	Please non	Negotiating	Answer
2	Hey, méfiez vous. Go far. I don't want to see you	Threatening the boy	Criticism of the teacher's action	2	Jamais, I am also a student.	Rebelling	Threat
3	OK! Continue to behave like a mad man and I will let you in. n'importe quoi.	Insulting the boy	Anger Insult	3	La discrimination is not good.	Denouncing injustice	Insult
4	So you know God hein. Vraiment!	Mocking the learner	Silence	4	Me, teacher? N'importe quoi!	Insulting back	Laughters noise in the class
				5	I cannot go hein. Je m'enganban.	Challenging the teacher	Laughters in the class Order
				6	I am a student. I also pay. Je wanda. La Nga ci hein.	Protesting	Anger Instructions given
				7	Teacher, it is not normal. Dieu est là.	Complaining	Mockery

Table 1 gives an account of tag-switching as used by the teacher and the learners involved in this conversation. As indicated, the teacher used four examples of tag-switching. In the first example, she used a directive in English to welcome Ava the female girl (Ava, the girl come in) before switching to French to reject the naughty male learner. (You, va en balade.) The use of "you" indicates indifference towards that learner who has a name. This switch to French clearly violates the politeness rule of generosity and agreement because in a very untactful manner, the teacher rejects one of the latecomers. The teacher's act of injustice is face-threatening and implies that the other student has less value. The purposeful flouting of the sympathy, generosity, agreement and tact maxims by the teacher

negatively affects the student. The student's reaction (I am also a student.) is a criticism; it suggests disapproval as well as frustration. The directive in French (va en balade) expresses indifference: as the teacher does not stand that student, she doesn't want to see him at all. As probably expected by the teacher, the reaction of the male student and the class (screams) suggest that they disagree with her. The first tag-switching by the learner is produced to negotiate (please non). Through the incorporation of the french element (noon), the learner is trying to arouse feelings of sympathy or pity in the teacher to encourage her to admit him into the classroom. However, this expressive by the learner spirals the indifference of the teacher. The explanation she offers even translates

mockery (il y'a des élèves sur qui on peut compter, d'autres sur qui on ne peut pas): it is a mere insult. As a result, the student who perceived sarcasm reacted violently. Example 2 (jamais, I am also a student) shows that the insertion of a French word "jamais" portrays rebellion. By using it, the student expresses his determination to disobey. By so doing, he refuses on purpose to comply with the maxims of politeness prescribed by Leech (1983). Disobeying is a face-threatening act that harms the teacher's face of the learner. Secondly, defying the teacher is an insult to her personality but it is obvious that it is a response to the teacher's discourtesy.

In Example 2, the teacher also produced a french tag to threaten the heady boy (Hey, méfiez vous) before reiterating his instruction in English (go far. I don't want to see you). The use of French here expresses determination, seriousness as well as the urge to communicate because English is often a barrier. The code-switching indicates the teacher's desire to hurt the learner effectively. These words are uttered by the teacher to criticise the student's behaviour in order to help him improve. This face-threatening act hurts the learner who reacts using complaint and criticism. The student's criticism does not yield the expected outcomes. That is why in Example 3, the teacher indirectly threatened the learner and inserted a French expression in her sentence to insult the naughty learner. (OK, continue to behave like a mad man and I will let you in. n'importe quoi). The use of "n'importe quoi" shows the state of anger of the teacher: it is a purposeful flouting of the tact, sympathy, generosity and approbation maxim recommended by Leech (1983). The abusive words "mad man, n'importe quoi" are criticised by the learner who insulted back. It is obvious that they are indicative of conflict in the classroom. Likewise, the teacher's utterance has motivated the learner to insult the teacher, therefore not respecting the agreement, modesty, and tact maxims. In Example 4, the teacher used tag-switching to laugh at the learner who is calling God to rescue him. The use of "vraiment" here portrays doubt and amusement

since the learner's behaviour is in total contrast with God's commandments.

As far as the students are concerned, in this exchange, they used seven examples of tag-switching. The first example of tag-switching was produced by the male learner to beg the teacher (please noon). "The incorporation of a French word (noon) aims at negotiating in a bid to convince the teacher to let him in. This expressive fails to attain the intended goal because the teacher drives him away and allows the girl to go in. facing such a discriminatory action by the teacher, the class reacts by screaming. This scream shows that the remaining learners in the class are scandalised.

In line with Leech's (1983) theory of politeness, we can say that disharmony between the teacher and the learners, is transparent in the language used in this interaction. Screams from the learners in the classroom context express disapproval of some of the teacher's actions. The tact and agreement maxims are clearly flouted here. In Example 2, conflict continues to be displayed; the learner's reaction is an overt strategy to defy the teacher (jamais, I am also a student). The use of "jamais" in French indicates the learner's determination to disobey. The rebellion expressed through this word equally denounced injustice. The assertive used by the same student in English is enough evidence (I am also a student). This therefore means that the speech acts carried out are obvious indicators of conflict between the teacher and the learners. For instance, the students are not supposed to defy their teacher so openly especially when they are wrong. If we consider Leech (1983) theory of politeness, the use of "jamais" here is tantamount to impoliteness because it contradicts the maxim of agreement (the learner used the wrong tone when talking to the teacher). It equally violates the maxims of tact and modesty. In Example 3, the student used a French word (la discrimination) to blame the teacher. He denounced discrimination with the intention of prompting her to change her mind. Unfortunately, the perlocutionary effect of his utterance is anger manifested through insults as shown in Example 4 (Me teacher? n'importe quoi aussi) used by the learner to insult back the

teacher. This discourteous act provokes laughters and noise in the class. The perlocutionary effect of this utterance is classroom disruption.

In fact, in Example 4, an expressive is used by the learner in English to express anger and threaten the teacher. Then the switch to French is rude. It is obvious that the student's answer damages the teacher's face in the classroom where he is supposed to be an authority. The Exchange of insults by the teacher and the learner indicates the intensity of disagreement. In line with Leech's theory of politeness, we can say that language use in situations of disharmony in the classroom setting is often characterised by violence. In Example 5, the learner makes use of tag-switching to challenge the teacher's decision. (I cannot go hein Mme. Je m'enganban). The student stands to defy the teacher. In English, the assertive (I cannot go hein Mme) is intended to disobey, protest. By contradicting the teacher, the learner displays arrogance. The switch to French and Ewondo was intended to amuse the class and create disruption. The learner's language constantly violates the norms of politeness defined by leech. Since courtesy is the key norm during classroom talk, the teacher and the student must be courteous all the time when addressing each other. Arrogance is then a signal of conflict during class interaction.

Example 6 was used to protest and argue with the teacher (I am a student, I also pay. Je wanda). Here the student uses two assertives in English to express dismay and inform the teacher he has the right to be in class. (I am a student. I also pay). These arguments portray headiness and anger. Then the switch to camfranglais is used to despise openly (je wanda. La Nga ci hein). The use of Camfranglais element "je wanda" or "la Nga" during an EFL lesson is considered very rude in the instructional context of the class. The student bluntly violates the sympathy and modesty maxim by teasing the teacher. By speaking French combined with Camfranglais, the student shows total disrespect. This means that the language used by the student lacks humility in the way he uses language. In Example 7, the student uses two assertives to complain about the teacher's behaviour and attitude

towards him. The first statement is in English (Teacher it is not normal); it expresses some worry because the learner seems to condemn injustice. The second utterance in French portrays the power of the roudy student. Reference to God (Dieu est là) sought to influence the teacher's emotion but it did not attain its objectives: the perlocutionary effect of the student's last tag-switching is mockery on the part of the teacher.

In a nutshell, the various uses of tag-switching in the above exchange show that in situations of conflict like the one depicted here, the teacher used code-switching to sensitize the learners on the stakes of poor classroom behaviour. The different speech acts carried out by the teacher equally prove that tag-switching is often used as a strategy of classroom management. By means of acts such as welcoming, driving away, threatening, insulting, mocking and criticizing, the teacher manipulates learners in order to help them achieve their instructional and educational goals. In most of the teacher-student interactions we analysed, the linguistic barrier urged EFL teachers to code-switch because many francophone learners do not understand English well. As far as students are concerned, they used to tag-switch to carry out as varied acts as negotiating, rebelling, protesting, denouncing, insulting or insulting back, complaining, arguing and criticizing. They also code-switch to express a variety of emotions such as dismay, anger, surprise, revolt, enthusiasm. The observation of EFL lessons in 35 classes revealed that the frequency of code-switching is high during conflict. We also noticed that disharmony and discourtesy are intrinsically related since in most cases, teachers and learners violated norms of politeness when they interacted in situations of conflict. It is then clear that context influences language use. The next section also exemplifies some instances of inter-sentential switching.

1.1.2 The use of inter-sentential switching

Appel & Muysken (1987:118) remark that: "inter-sentential switching is the alternation in a single discourse between two languages, where the switching occurs after a sentence in the first language has been completed and the next

sentence starts with a new language.” This means that a part of the sentence is written in one language and the rest in another language. Many examples of inter-sentential switching were found in the corpus. Inter-sentential switching was also frequently used to lecture the learners on the negative impact of rude behaviour in class. Exchange 57 below illustrates the use of inter-sentential switching.

Exchange 57: Tle C, Collège Moderne, February 2016, Douala

Situation: People were about to start oral presentations. There was a student-teacher in the classroom. Students continued to make noise.

Teacher: Good afternoon class. I hope all the groups are ready and we have a guest today who came to see how good you are in English.

A student: Vraiment Mme, I go show you.

Class: Aie, Pata. Ha ha ha.

Teacher: Who said that? Toi Pata, Comporte-toi comme le vieil élève que tu es, Go and kneel down bastard.

Another student: That is good Teacher, Il exagère.

Teacher: People are in terminale but they have water in their brain. Group 1, in front.

A presenter: Good afternoon. Our topic is natural disaster and their consequences (another interrupts him).

A male student: Parles fort, c’est quoi? Speak aloud hein!

Teacher: Look at that street boy, on t’a pas appris à demander la parole?

A male student: Ekiécé, haaa.

Teacher: Tsuipp, shut up Baba. Un salaud comme ça. Il n’arrive même pas à présenter son travail mais il bavarde. Ouvre encore ta gueule là.

Baba: Madame je ne suis pas un animal pour avoir la gueule, you should say bouche.

Class: (Chorally) haha ha le français là est dur hein, French is not easy.

Teacher: Tsuipp. Ferme ça, Go out, rascal.

Baba: Pardon, sorry Mme.

The above exchange contains many examples of inter-sentential switching. They are presented in the table Below.

Table 2. Some Examples of Inter-Sentential Switching in EX 57

N°	Teacher’s utterances			N°	Learner’s utterances		
	Locution	Illocution	Perlocution		Locution	Illocution	Perlocution
1	Toi Pata, comporte-toi comme le vieil élève que tu es, Go and kneel down bastard.	Shouting Insulting Punishing	Advising Punishing	1	Vraiment Mme, I go show you.	Teasing the teacher Disrupting the clas	Laughters Angers (teacher)
				2	That is good Teacher, il exagère.	Blaming their mate	Silence
2	Look at that street boy, on t’a pas appris à demander la parole?	Insulting Criticising the learner’s attitude	Impolite answer	3	Parles fort, c’est quoi ? Speak aloud hein!	Criticising	Sigh
			Silence	4	Madame je ne suis pas un animal pour avoir la gueule, you should say bouche.	Talking back Challenging	Laughters

3	Tsuipp, shut up Baba. Un salaud comme ça. Il n'arrive même pas à présenter son travail mais il bavarde. Ouvre encore ta gueule là.	Threatening Condemning	Silence	5	haha ha le français là est dur hein, French is not easy.	Mocking	Indifference
4	Tsuipp. Ferme ça. Go out, rascal.	Lecturing the noisemaker	Apology	6	Pardon madame, sorry teacher	Apologizing	Indifference

Clearly indicates that Exchange 57 the teacher used four examples of inter-sentential switching are produced to carry out different acts. These acts are generally prompted by the student's refusal to comply with instructions. Example 1 is made up of two directives in French and in English respectively. (*Toi Pata, comporte-toi comme le vieil élève que tu es*). The French sentence is used to shout at the noisemaker to restore order. It is equally an implied criticism and an insult because the teacher seems to tell the learner that he is too old but his behaviour does not reflect his age. The switch to English (*go and kneel down, bastard*) signals the disapproval of the teacher as well as the eagerness to repress unruly classroom comportment. Though the teacher intends to advise the learner, the language used is insulting and humiliating. If we consider Leech's (1983) theory of politeness applied in this work, we can say that the use of explicit insult such as "vieil élève or bastard" portray violence since they hurt, even damage the dignity of the learner. These acts of insulting, shouting and punishing flout the maxims of sympathy, tact agreement since they contribute in dispraising the student. The French utterance here plays the role of reminder as the teacher tells the noisemaker to change his attitude; the English utterance has a special function since the teacher uses it as a way of regaining authority by punishing the learner. The insult "bastard" aims at humiliating the learner for him to change.

The second example of the inter-sentential switching insults the learner (look at that street boy) and criticizes his attitude (*on ne t'a pas appris à demander la parole?*). The use of English indicates the teacher's anger. She uses an insult in English to call him to express disgust.

The assertive combined with expressive in French show that the teacher is scandalized by the student's action. The switch to French is tantamount to criticism: through the rhetorical question "on ne t'a pas appris à demander la parole?" the teacher attempts to let the class know this noisemaker lacks good manners. French is used to highlight the bad behaviour of the learner as well as to teach them the importance of turn taking in conversations. This act by the teacher yields good perlocutionary outcomes expressed by the positive reaction of the class (exclamation conveying mockery).

The third example of inter-sentential switching used by the teacher translates her anger; in the English utterance, she uses a directive to manage the student's rude behaviour. (*Shut up Baba*). This switch to French portrays the teacher's impatience as she has already called the class to order repeatedly without success. The insult used in French signals disharmony (*un salaud comme toi. Il n'arrive meme pas à presenter son travail mais il bavarde. Ouvre encore ta gueule*). In these sentences in French, the teacher carries out the different acts: insulting, mocking and threatening respectively. This shows that there is no harmony between the interactants. In the light of Leech's theory of politeness, acts such as the ones highlighted above, are not in conformity with generosity and approbation; they instead maximize the expression of ideas that mitigate benefit to the other. In this specific example of inter-sentential switching, language use does not enable to establish and maintain comity in the classroom because of the lack of cooperation by students. In the last example of inter-sentential switching used by the teacher, the use of two directives indicates the teacher is tired of negotiating. In French she commands

the learner to stop talking (*ferme ça*), before dismissing him from the class in English (*go out, rascal*). The use of “*rascal*” at the end of the English utterance portrays disagreement. By driving the learner away, the teacher intends to go on with teaching in the classroom. It means that in a situation of disharmony like this one, the language used by classroom interactants often disagree with norms of politeness.

In the above interaction, the learners also used 5 examples of inter-sentential switching. The first example reflects the desire to disrupt the class. The first sentence is in French (*vraiment Mme?*). It is used to tease the teacher who even has a trainee in class. In the sentence in pidgin, the learner promises to trouble the teacher (*I go show you*). This first example of inter-sentential switching aims at amusing the class. The targeted objectives are attained since the class reacts by laughing. However, the student’s act arouses feelings of anger in the teacher who code-switches to shout, insult, and send punish. The use of pidgin in the EFL class is a purposeful act of disrespect because Pidgin English is prohibited in the EFL class. Language use here then contradicts the maxim of agreement and sympathy pruned by Leech (1985) to establish a peaceful atmosphere in class.

In Example 2 by the learner, the English assertive is used by another learner to congratulate the teacher. The assertive in French is a criticism of the classmate’s abnormal behaviour (*il exagère*). There is a clear indication of disharmony because the maxim of sympathy and agreement is flouted since the speaker blames his classmate for misbehaving in class. The switch to French then shows that the remark is addressed to their rude classmate while the praise in English is addressed to the teacher. In Example 3 by the learner, inter-sentential switching from French to English to criticize their classmate (*parle fort, c’est quoi?*). This directive in French is used with the intention of urging the classmate to raise his voice. This desire is reiterated in the directive in English (*speak loudly*). Orders are inherently impolite in an equal-to-equal relationship. As a matter of fact, the addressee that is another classmate reacts by indifference. The signal shows

contempt and therefore flouts the maxim of modesty and tact since the expression of words that dispraise the other is maximized in this interaction. Example 4 is a reaction to the teacher’s threat. In French, the learner talks back to the teacher “*Mme je ne suis pas un animal pour avoir la gueule*”. In fact, this assertive aims at pointing out the fact that the teacher does not speak good French. The laughs in the class show the effect of this sentence. Mockery is thus the perlocutionary effect of that sentence. The switch to English is also meant to challenge the teacher “*you should say bouche*”. Mockery in an interaction violates the maxim of modesty and sympathy since the dignity of the teacher is minimised. They were sometimes responses to the learner’s indiscipline.

The fifth example of switching is used to laugh at the teacher. In French (*ha ha, le français là est dur hein*), an assertive is used to laugh at the low proficiency of the EFL Teacher in French; in English, the assertive (*French is not easy*) reinforces mockery. However, the perlocutionary effect expected is not achieved as the teacher responds to mockery by indifference. However, as he continues to laugh, the teacher sends him out by insulting him (*ferme ça, go out, rascal*). The use of “*rascal*” by the teacher here portrays anger and disapprobation. This directive prompts the learner to apologize using an inter-sentential switching. (*Pardon noon, sorry Mme*).

In a nutshell, all the things done with inter-sentential were not always carefully planned. They are often situational responses to the learners’ indiscipline. As a matter of fact, because of the learners’ poor classroom behaviour, the teacher often consciously or unconsciously violates the norms of politeness to attain their goals.

1.2 The Pragmatic Functions of Code-Switching in EFL Conflict Situations

The results of classroom observation and the analysis of the corpus revealed that code switching serves several functions in situations of conflict in the EFL classroom.

Table 3. Functions of the Tag-Switching Used by Teachers

Number of exchanges	Function	Occurrence	Percentage
70	mocking	14	51.86%
	Insulting	11	40.74%
	consoling	02	07.41 %
TOTAL	03	27	100

Table 4. Functions of Tag-Switching Used by Learners

Number of exchanges	Function	Occurrence	Percentage
70	mocking	15	75%
	Explaining	05	25%
	Insulting back	05	25%
TOTAL	03	20	100

The two tables above give an overview of the functions of tag-switching as used by EFL teachers and their learners in the various contexts of conflict. For instance, the analysis of the exchanges reveals that EFL teachers had the tendency to use tag-switching in situations of conflict to mock stubborn learners after they had called them to order repeatedly. The superiority of the teachers is transparent in their use of code-switching. Under normal circumstances,

EFL teachers switched to French rarely but when there was conflict characterised by confrontation, the overwhelming majority resorted to French to make their instructions respected and deal with poor classroom. As the main actor of classroom talk, the teacher frequently resorted to French in situations of disharmony with a view to educate children in class.

Table 5. Functions of the Inter-Sentential Switching Used by Teachers

N° of Exchanges	Functions	Occurrences	Percentage
	Criticising	12	38.70 %
	Mocking	11	35.48 %
	Insulting	05	16.12 %
	Threatening	03	09.67 %
70	03	31	100

Table 6. Functions of the Inter Sentential Switching Used by Students

N° of exchanges	Functions	Occurrences	Percentage
	Contradicting	30	27.02%
	Teasing	30	27.02 %
	Challenging	15	13.51%
	Blaming	15	13.51%
	Begging	10	09.09 %
	Complaining	05	04.50 %
	Despising	05	04.50%
70	07	111	100

The tables above present the frequency as well as the functions of inter-sentential switching

during EFL classroom conversations in situations of disharmony. An analysis of the data

culled from teacher-student exchanges during observation shows that most students used intersentential switching to tease (27.02%) and to contradict (27.02%) the teacher. These acts which represent a threat for the teacher's face in the classroom context, suggest conflict. Similarly, most of the time, EFL teachers used inter-sentential-switching in situations of conflict to criticise (38%), to mock(35%), to insult(16%) and to threaten(09%) . These acts are face-threatening and signal conflict. Intersentential switching is sometimes used by EFL students to criticise the negative behaviour of teachers in situations of disharmony; EFL teachers use this type of switching to insult the roudy learners and threaten them to establish order in class. Based on the acts carried out by teachers and learners, it is obvious that, in the context of conflict, teachers often sacrifice politeness to fulfill other aims in the class.

As observed during EFL lessons, the learners in the classes observed, use intersentential switching to tease the teacher. By so doing, they show proof of discourtesy; the flouting of politeness maxims of agreement, approbation and even tact because as learners, they are supposed to obey the teacher for learning to be effective. By challenging teachers, the learners disrespect them; consequently, they flout the maxim of modesty so recommended in class. Finally, it is then obvious that in situations of conflict, the language used by classroom interactants show that there is lack of comity. As a matter of fact, the acts performed as well as the functions of inter-sentential switching demonstrate that there is little cooperation on the part of learners, and this compels EFL teachers to use discourteous language when interacting with students who often display unacceptable behaviour in class. It is obvious that code-switching is then sometimes used to solve the conflicts that arise in the classroom; Sometimes, it often generates conflict in an unplanned way. This is normal because during observation, we realised that dismissing was generally the ultimate resolution teachers resorted to during conflict. The types of speech act carried out in teacher-student conversations were characteristically face-threatening. These

acts were inherently impolite because they affect the image of the interactants as well as their freedom. Considering the asymmetric relation between teachers and learners, acts such as disagreeing, begging, teasing and challenging are not expected from teachers nor learners in the classroom: they are simply the mirror of an unhealthy teacher-student relationship.

Conclusion

Finally, we observed during class observation that the high frequency of code switching sometimes stands as an indicator of teacher-student conflict because it generally occurred following the learner's lack of cooperation during EFL lessons. This means that, as reported by most teachers during the survey, conflict sometimes forces the teacher to tailor their style to the situation in class. In addition, the classroom observation done in the selected schools revealed that for teachers, code switching frequently served the following purposes in situations of conflict in the classroom: explanation, sensitization, insult, mockery, criticism, shouting, threatening. It appears as a strategy of class management when the other options have failed. In a similar vein, learners from diverse backgrounds did the following actions with code-switching in situations of conflict: provoking, contradicting, disagreeing, defending, complaining, begging, insulting, and despising just to name a few. In the process of interaction during teacher-student conflict, maxims of politeness are purposely or unconsciously flouted. The data analysis revealed that in all the classroom situations, language use is not haphazard. The different actions done demonstrated that politeness is rarely respected during interaction in conflict situations. In this paper, we have also shown that conflict brings about discourtesy in some situations and in others, discourtesy brings about conflict. It is then the main indicator of conflict during teacher -learner talk in the classroom.

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